

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF THE PRINCIPLES OF ANTI-CORRUPTION COMPLIANCE CONTROL.

Umid Karshiev

(ORCID Number)

(0009-0009-6198-3745)

(umidqarshiyev1999@gmail.com)

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Annotation: This thesis reflects the principles of anti-corruption compliance control. In general, the principles are important for every area of law, so these principles have been discussed in detail. The meaning of principle briefly has been touched upon. Moreover, its essence has been fully revealed.

Keywords: Principle, anti-corruption compliance control, corruption, governance principle, risk management principle, prevention principle, transparency principle, training principle, due diligence principle, investigation principle, reporting principle, enforcement principle, continuous improvement principle. Before discussing the principles of anti-corruption compliance control, it is necessary to define the meaning of the word principle. Philosophers, lawyers and sociologists use the term "principle" (Latin - principium) to express the law of existence, the internal logic of the studied phenomenon. The principle category is inextricably linked with the "lawfulness" and "essence" categories¹. Based on this point of view, it can be noted that the essence of anti-corruption compliance control is reflected in the content of its main principles. Anti-corruption compliance control principles cover its entire internal structure and content.

The principles of anti-corruption compliance control are discussed below. It has several principles. In particular, the principle of "Governance" should be an integral part of the governance structure of the organization. The "Governance" principle of anti-corruption compliance control refers to systematic measures implemented by organizations to prevent, identify and respond to corruption risks. This principle is designed to create an effective internal control system that ensures transparency, accountability and integrity in all aspects of the organization's activities.

Overall, the "Governance" principle of anti-corruption compliance control is essential for organizations to operate with integrity, comply with legal and regulatory requirements, and protect their reputation and brand value. By implementing effective anti-corruption compliance measures, organizations can create a culture of transparency, accountability and trust, thereby ensuring long-term sustainable growth and success.

The principle of "risk management" is also reflected in international standards. Anti-corruption compliance control should be developed based on the assessment of corruption risks of the organization. The principle of "risk management" refers to the measures and policies adopted by the organization to prevent and detect corruption in the organization. This principle includes the identification and assessment of the risk of corruption in the organization, the use of preventive and investigative measures, as well as the monitoring and verification of the effectiveness of these measures. The principle of anti-corruption compliance control is crucial

¹ Odilqoriyev X.T. Davlat va huquq nazariyasi. Darslik. – Toshkent. «Adolat», 2018. – 528 b.

in reducing or eliminating the risk of financial and reputational losses, legal liability and damage to trust in the organization caused by corruption. It also ensures that the organization complies with anti-corruption laws, regulations and ethical standards. Anti-corruption compliance controls may include regular employee training, implementing an anti-corruption policy, conducting due diligence on third-party contractors, internal audits, and reporting any corrupt practices to the appropriate authorities. The anti-corruption compliance control principle should be fully explained to all employees to ensure they understand their roles and responsibilities in preventing and reporting corruption. In addition, complying with anti-corruption compliance controls should be regularly monitored and reviewed to ensure that the organization is effective in reducing the risk of corruption.

The "Prevention" principle of anti-corruption compliance control refers to active measures taken by organizations to prevent corrupt behavior. This principle seeks to ensure that the risk of corruption is proactively addressed before it occurs, not after it occurs. There are several reasons why the preventive principle of anti-corruption compliance control is crucial. Firstly, it helps companies avoid the potentially costly legal and reputational consequences of corrupt practices. Secondly, it ensures that the company maintains a transparent and ethical corporate culture, which is essential for building trust with stakeholders.

Overall, the "Prevention" principle of anti-corruption compliance control emphasizes the importance of companies taking active measures to prevent corruption in their activities. By implementing effective compliance programs, companies can avoid negative legal and reputational consequences while maintaining a transparent and ethical corporate culture.

The fourth principle of anti-corruption compliance control is the principle of "transparency". The principle of "transparency" includes openness, honesty and accountability in all dealings. This requires transparency in reporting, availability of data, access to data, clear communication and training. Together, these aspects help organizations detect and prevent corruption, maintain stakeholder trust, and ensure compliance with laws and regulations.

The "Training" principle of anti-corruption compliance control is an important aspect of prevention and detection of corrupt activities in the organization. Key aspects that should be fully explained when implementing an anti-corruption compliance training program include:

- 1) Syllabus Objectives: The syllabus should clearly state the aims and objectives of the programme. This includes the importance of preventing corruption, the benefits of compliance to the organization, and the consequences of non-compliance.
- 2) Understanding Anti-Corruption Laws: It is important to educate employees on the various anti-corruption laws that apply to the organization. This includes explaining local laws and regulations, standards, and international norms as well.
- 3) Recognizing Corrupt Practices: Employees should be taught how to recognize red flags that indicate corrupt practices, including potential bribery, fraud, or other unethical behavior. They should also be encouraged to report any suspected violations through appropriate channels.
- 4) Compliance Policies and Procedures: Employees should familiarize themselves with the organization's compliance policies and procedures, including the Code of Conduct, Anti-

Corruption Policy and related HR policies. They also need to understand their obligations as employees, including their obligation to report any violations.

5) Teaching Methods: The training program should use a variety of teaching methods to ensure that employees fully understand the material. This includes interactive sessions, case studies and scenarios, as well as tests and assessments to test learning.

6) Continuous training and updates: Anti-corruption training should be an ongoing process, with regular updates and refresher courses to keep staff up to date with any changes in laws or policies. This helps reinforce the importance of compliance and ensures that employees are vigilant against corrupt practices.

Raising legal awareness is important in the fight against corruption. This can be achieved through training and educational activities. Implementation of the above measures is the main part of the compliance control activity.

Even in the current era, it is important to learn enough about the opposite party when entering into economic, political, and even social relations. Anti-corruption compliance control should include due diligence processes to assess the corruption risk of third parties, such as suppliers or agents.

“Due diligence” principle of anti-corruption compliance control requires organizations to comprehensively assess their business partners, customers and third-party service providers to ensure they have taken appropriate anti-corruption measures. The purpose of this principle is to minimize the risk of bribery and corruption in business operations, as well as to protect the reputation and integrity of the organization.

In order to comply with the principle of due diligence, organizations must conduct a risk assessment to identify potential risks associated with their business partners and third-party service providers². This assessment should take into account factors such as the nature of the relationship, the level of government involvement, the location of the business partner or service provider, and the industry or sector.

Based on this risk assessment, organizations should develop and implement appropriate anti-corruption measures, such as contractual provisions, compliance training and monitoring mechanisms, to ensure that their business partners and service providers comply with applicable anti-corruption laws and regulations.

Overall, organizations should regularly review and update their due diligence procedures to ensure they remain effective and relevant to changes in the business environment. This review should also consider feedback from employees, customers and other stakeholders to continuously improve the organization's anti-corruption compliance monitoring program.

One of the important aspects in the fight against corruption is reporting. The essence of the “reporting” principle is that anti-corruption compliance control should include mechanisms for reporting suspected corruption and responding to such reports. Measures such as

² Biegelman, Martin T., and Biegelman, Daniel R., Foreign Corrupt Practices Act Compliance Handbook: Protecting Your Company from Bribery and Corruption, Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, 2010.

whistleblowing policies and reporters' protection should be developed. As a logical continuation of this process, appropriate measures should be taken regarding the received message and information about corruption. In particular, the principle of "Investigations" provides such measures.

The "Investigation" principle of anti-corruption compliance control is an important aspect of prevention and detection of corrupt activities in the organization. This includes conducting a thorough and impartial investigation into reports or suspicions of corruption, bribery or other unethical conduct. This principle aims to ensure that all allegations of corruption are taken seriously and investigated promptly and thoroughly. It requires establishing clear procedures for reporting any suspected corrupt activity and ensuring that these procedures are available to all employees and interested parties.

The investigation process should be carried out by a competent and independent team, which may include internal or external auditors. The team must have the necessary skills and resources to conduct a comprehensive investigation, including gathering and analysing evidence, interviewing witnesses, and presenting findings. The investigation should be conducted based on the legal framework and guidelines of the country or region in which the organization operates. This principle requires confidentiality during the investigation to protect the complainant and the accused from undue harm. The investigation principle is important in anti-corruption compliance control because it ensures that any corrupt activity is detected and eliminated before it escalates, thereby protecting the reputation of the organization and ensuring that it operates legally and responsibly.

It is the principle of "enforcement" that reflects the need to include disciplinary measures against employees who violate the organization's anti-corruption policy. The "enforcement" principle of anti-corruption compliance control is related to the consistent application of consequences when violations of anti-corruption policies and regulations are detected. It involves the creation of a system of active monitoring, reporting and punishment of offenses including but not limited to bribery, fraud, embezzlement and racketeering and other forms of the corruption.

Effective enforcement includes identifying potential risks, implementing appropriate controls to reduce or eliminate those risks, and investigating and punishing any violations. This includes formal disciplinary measures such as fines, termination of employment or contracts, and legal action. In addition, appropriate risk management processes, including regular reviews by internal and external parties, should be conducted to ensure that anti-corruption compliance control are properly implemented throughout the organization.

By fully explaining the enforcement principle of anti-corruption compliance control, organizations can develop a culture of transparency and accountability, which helps reduce the risk of corrupt practices and increase public confidence in business relationships. This, in turn, helps to create a fair and equal environment that benefits all interested parties.

The last principle is the principle of "Constant improvement"³. Based on this principle, anti-corruption compliance control should be regularly reviewed, evaluated and updated to ensure that they remain effective and adapt to changing circumstances.

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4. ISO 37001 – Anti-Bribery Management Systems.

³ Andrew Henderson. "Understanding and implementing ISO 37001 – Anti-Bribery Management Systems". Routledge, 2017.